

About 57, 42, and 27% of IR42, IR56, and IR36 plants sampled showed RTBV and RTSV. The other sampled plants showed RTBV only. However, all IR50 and IR54 plants sampled reacted to RTBV only. All plants of the susceptible check TN1 reacted to both RTBV and RTSV. No variety reacted to the presence of RTSV only (Table 1).

Attempts to recover the virus from the infected plants were made using *N. virescens*. Recovery was successful from plants infected with RTBV and RTSV. In the recovery tests involving 52 plants infected with RTBV alone, 1,408 seedlings were inoculated with 326 insects that were given 4 days acquisition time on the plants. No positive transmission was obtained regardless of variety (Table 2).

This is the first finding that shows a connection between the presence of RTBV alone in varieties with a high level of resistance to the vector, and with fairly low percentage of tungro infection. Although infected, these plants will not serve as virus source for the spread of the disease. □

Table 1. Presence of RTV complex on 5 IR varieties as detected by the latex agglutination test.

Variety	Reaction to		Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of		
	GLH ^a	RTV ^b		RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR36	MR	S	15	4	11	0
IR42	MR	S	14	8	6	0
IR50	R	I	13	0	13	0
IR54	R	I	15	0	15	0
IR56	R to MR ^c	S	12	5	7	0
TN1	S	S	13	13	0	0

^a Data from IRRI Entomology Department. ^bGreenhouse mass-screening results, IRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0 = 30% infection, resistant (R); 31-60%, intermediate (I); 61-100%, susceptible (S). ^c Reaction varies from resistant (R) to moderately resistant (MR).

Table 2. Virus recovery from plants containing both RTBV and RTSV or RTBV alone using the vector insect *N. virescens*.

Variety	RTBV and RTSV ^a			RTBV alone ^c	
	Plants tested ^b (no.)	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (no.)	Plants tested (no.)	Insects tested (no.)
IR36	4	34	24	11	97
IR4	8	79	66	6	56
IR50	—	—	—	13	55
IR54	—	—	—	15	14
IR5	5	43	27	7	44
TN	113	108	71	—	—

^a A dash indicates no recovery test conducted because no plant reacted to the presence of the virus.

^b Virus was recovered from all plants tested. ^c No plant or insect tested yielded the virus.

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice yield loss caused by leaffolder damage at tillering stage

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Yield loss caused by leaffolder infestation at tillering stage was studied in the greenhouse by artificially infesting 55-day-old IR20 plants with 0, 1, 2, or 3 larvae/tiller. Each 30-cm pot had 5 tillers at infestation. The experiment was replicated 6 times.

The number of leaves damaged and total leaves in each infested tiller was recorded when larvae pupated. Percent of leaves damaged was calculated. Grains from individual tillers were collected at maturity, percentage of unfilled grains was calculated, and grain weight was estimated (see table).

Damage and yield in leaffolder-infested IR20^a

Larvae (no.) /tiller	Leaves damaged ^b (%)	Mean yield ^b (g/tiller)	Yield reduction (%)	Unfilled (%)
0		2.1 a		9.6
1	43.6 a	1.1 b	48.8	29.1
2	58.8 b	1.0 b	52.2	26.2
3	70.8 b	0.9 b	56.9	29.0

^a Mean of 30 tillers. ^b Means followed by common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Leaf damage was significantly lower for plants infested with 1 larva/tiller, but the yield did not differ significantly among the treatments. Yield was reduced by 49 to 57% for all treatments and 26 to 29% of grains were unfilled.

The regression of grain yield on the percentage of leaves damaged, and

1. Regression of grain yield on percentage of leaves damaged by leaffolder. (n = 120)

percentage of unfilled grains on the percentage of leaves damaged was studied. The regression equation for grain yield on percentage of leaves damaged was $\hat{Y} = 1.9234 - 0.0149 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.409 (Fig. 1). A 10% increase in damaged leaves reduced yield by 0.15 g/tiller.

The regression equation for percentage of unfilled grains on percentage of damaged leaves was $\hat{Y} = 13.3005 + 0.2276 X$, with a significant ($P = 0.05$) r^2 value of 0.193 (Fig. 2). A 10% increase in the damaged leaves increased the unfilled grains by 2%. □

2. Regression of percentage of unfilled grains on percentage of leaves damaged by leaf-folder. (n = 120)

Rice yield losses caused by leaffolder damage to the flag leaf

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is an important rice insect in Tamil Nadu. Infestation is common at maximum tiller or flag leaf stages.

Flag leaves of potted IR20 plants were artificially infested with one 4th-instar larva/tiller. Feeding was confined to the flag leaf. Uninfested plants were the check. Four days after infestation, the larva was removed and damage was recorded as percent of the total area of the leaf. Grains from individual infested tillers were collected at maturity and percent unfilled grains was calculated. Healthy grain weight was recorded and lost grain yield was calculated.

Flag leaf damage ranged from 5 to 85% in different tillers and was categorized as <25, 26-50, 51-75, and >75%. Leaf area damage up to 50% reduced mean yield per tiller by 47%. When insect damage exceeded 75%, yield was reduced 70% (see table).

1. Regression of grain yield on percentage of flag leaf area damaged by leaffolder. Top: 2. Regression of unfilled grains on percentage of flag leaf area damaged by leaffolder.

Effect of flag leaf damage by leaffolder on rice grain yield.^a

Leaf area damage (%)	Mean yield (g/tiller)	Yield reduction (%)
<25	1.1	47
26-50	1.1	
51-75	1.2	46
>75	0.7	70
Uninfested	2.2	

^aMean of 8 replications.

The regression of grain yield on percent of leaf area damaged and percent of unfilled grains on percent of leaf area damaged was studied.

The regression equation of grain yield on the percentage area damaged was $\hat{Y} = 1.7274 - 0.0132 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.418 (Fig. 1). A 10% increase in leaffolder damage reduced yield by 0.13 g/tiller.

The regression equation of percentage unfilled grains on percent flag leaf damage was $\hat{Y} = 9.8758 + 0.4522 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.624 (Fig. 2). A 10% increase in flag leaf damage increased unfilled grains by 4.5%/tiller. □

Efficacy of insecticides against rice whorl maggot

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Chlorpyrifos 10 G (coroban), carbosulfen 3 G (furadan), and monocrotophos 40 EC (Monocil) were tested for control of rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* at the NDUAT Crop Research Station during 1981 kharif. Saket 4 was

planted in 5 × 4m plots. Insecticides were applied to 10-day-old nursery seedlings 10 days after transplanting. Insecticide granules were broadcast and monocrotophos was sprayed. RWM infestation was recorded 30 days after transplanting